

Terracotta: An Artistry Measures to Develop Rural Women Entrepreneur

Paper Id : 19798 Submission Date : 2025-02-05 Acceptance Date : 2025-02-22 Publication Date : 2025-02-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14978812

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/remarking.php#8>

Smita Dubey

Research Scholar
Home Science
University Of Lucknow
Lucknow, U.P., India

Sarika Gupta

Assistant Professor
Commerce (Banking &
Insurance)
Deen Dayal Upadhyaya
Gorakhpur University
Gorakhpur, U.P., India

Abstract This research article explore the connection between terracotta handicraft tradition and the economic upliftment of rural women in Gorakhpur in Uttar Pradesh. The paper highlight the terracotta craft, which is regarded as specific artisan cultural heritage and is an income generating activity for many rural women. The Terracotta impact the rural women multidimensionally, such as deficiency of resources, socio-economic dependency and others. The paper also explore the factors likes, low literacy rate and socio-cultural barriers that restricts them in engaging fully in the terracotta handicraft industry. The study identifies that Self-Help Groups, initiatives of the government like ODOP, and skills development enable the women artisans in the respective craft to build an economic system where they acquire social recognition while creating a product, access marketable opportunities for earning, and grow in this skill-based self-dependent economy. The research advocates for strategies to overcome the existing challenges by integrating digital literacy, business training, and community awareness campaigns. This paper concludes that terracotta craftsmanship is not only vital for preserving cultural heritage but also a key driver of economic stability and empowerment for women in rural communities.

Keywords Terracotta, Woman artisan, Handicraft, Rural woman, Empowerment, Entrepreneur

Introduction

India has a very long and rich history with terracotta art that dates back thousands of years. The term Terracotta originate from the Latin word, which means "baked earth." Traces of which was found in the Indus Valley Civilization, which flourished between 2600 and 1700 BCE. This genre includes the Berni engravings, which are terracotta objects found in Mesopotamia around 1950 BC. Large-scale manufacture was also explored by the Greek Tanagta miniatures. The terracotta army of the Chinese emperor Jin-Shi-Hun, who ruled from 210 to 209 BC, is another important monument of this artistry.

Traces of Terracotta Art was also found in Nigeria and other territory of African continent. Terracotta art has a long history in India, dating back to the Indus Valley and up to the present. A number of states, including West Bengal, Punjab, Haryana, Hooghly, and Rajasthan's Molela Terracotta, have examples of it in the field. Because terracotta art incorporates all five elements—earth, fire, water, soil and sky—it is revered in India. An essential component of Indian culture and legacy in terracotta art. It includes a range of embellishments for earthen pots and, above all, a collection of sculptures in various sizes that have come to represent social, religious, and folkloric elements. It represents the rich artistic heritage of India. This artistic medium, is made from a unique type of orange-brown clay. encompasses the creation of ceramics, sculptures, and ornamental items.

Objective of study

This research paper is designed to explore the relationship between Terracotta art of Gorakhpur and its role in uplifting Rural Woman's Economic status.

Review of Literature

Gupta et al. (2020). Despite the contribution of terracotta artisans, the goods made by them do not reach the market and their artefacts are less recognized and get less support from policy makers. This research emphasizes support including skill enhancement programmes, financial incentives and marketing platforms for upliftment of the socio-economic status of terracotta artisans.

Khan et al. (2018). Terracotta products are often made using local resources and traditional techniques. This method is environmentally friendly. This paper discusses how terracotta artisans in Bangladesh use locally sourced soil and renewable sources of energy, which contribute to the conservation of natural resources

Yadav, U.S, Tripathi, R., Tripathi, M.A., & Kushwaha, J. (2022). In light of the current circumstances, the government ought to support the handicraft industry in order to enable migrant laborers to secure local employment and participate in the economic life of the surrounding areas. Also, promote community start ups and One District One Product (ODOP) to boost rural economy. However, the ODOP sector has regularly suffered from being informal and unorganized, due to lack of education, low capital and inadequate exposure to new technologies, inadequate institutional absence of market intelligence and a framework. Rural community artisans have enough skills to compete with the latest trend and fashion. They only require adequate support from the concerned authorities.

Rai, Madhu. (2017). Handicrafts are a unique expression of our community and culture. It generates foreign exchange earnings which is very important for economic growth and upliftment of our economy. The government should provide encouragement and support to explore the best of this handmade industry. The handicrafts sector needs to adopt competitive marketing strategies for the development of handicrafts that focus on accessible and transparent policy framework and potential policy measures

Farm, and Sridharan, (2013): The problem faced by women entrepreneurs in rural areas was being measured and the initiative was taken that most of the women entrepreneurs were judged as lacking strong leadership. The quality of his leadership was not as good as required to be a successful entrepreneur. There are many women entrepreneurs who face problems related to finance. The second place was financial inadequacy. Third place was lack of systematic development, no awareness about government scheme, no repayment of loan by participants, lack of education and other problems.

Hindustan Times. (jan 2024). Chief Minister Yogi Adityanath declared that the government's main focus is the empowerment of women. At an event in Gorakhpur, Prime Minister Narendra Modi stated that the Nari Shakti Vandan law, which gives women a 33% reservation in the Lok Sabha and state assemblies, demonstrates his dedication to empowering women to fight for their own rights and become self-sufficient. He gave sewing machines to 1150 women in Gorakhpur who had finished training as part of the Unnat Bharat Gram Abhiyan, which was run by the MP Education Council.

Main Text

Gorakhpur Terracotta

Gorakhpur Terracotta is especially important to the evolution of terracotta in the state of Uttar Pradesh. Terracotta artwork from Gorakhpur is a unique example of traditional art that has been shaped by customs and decades of wisdom. Here, the colors used are only natural, and the workmanship is mostly based on handicraft. Nearly a thousand different types of terracotta works are created by local artists. The villages of Aurangabad, Bharwalia, Amawa, Gulriya, Belwa, Raipur, Padri Bazar in Chargawan Block, and all Bhathat development blocks are the primary hubs of this art form. The majority of these clay artists are from the Prajapati community.

Many clay sculptures, ornamental items, kitchenware, and other products are made using terracotta art. Every region's terracotta manufacturing technique and expertise are always evident. It sets it apart from other areas' art. Gorakhpur's artists mostly work with natural materials. This comprises the pure clay that gives terracotta its 'lustre'. Particularly sourced from Aurangabad is dry clay. The color terracotta is this place's greatest specialty.

It comes from a certain type of "*Kabis Mitti*" and can also be found in Aurangabad in particular places as crust that is obtained at a particular time. It is created by pulverizing the *Khatdai* mango tree's bark with caustic soda in a mortar, sifting the mixture, and combining key components to create a terracotta color solution. It is red in color. All of these components are expertly used to make the well-known terracotta artwork.

Terracotta Artifacts

The main artifacts that the terracotta artists of Gorakhpur work on are ornamental, religious, cultural, and social. Aurangabad also produces a wide range of animal and bird clay sculptures. Religious issues include the creation of Arjun rath , Ganesh Deep, Lord Ganesh, Panchmukhi Lord Ganesh, Gautam Buddha Ji, Kalash Deep, Thali Deep, Thali Deepak Stand, Elephant, Tiger, and so on. Terracotta items are produced under the category of cultural issues and include musical ensembles, music sets, harmonium players, sitar players, tabla players, dancers, sarangi players, and so forth. Utensils,

bullock carts, camel carts, horse riders, camel riders, girls with lamps, girls with Kalash, etc. are examples of social issues.

Numerous themes and styles of terracotta sculptures are available for use as wall decorations. Some examples of these include horse, elephant tables, fish lamps, petal lamps, chandeliers, bells, wall lamps, and sets of terracotta sculptures. A wide variety of birds and animals, including fish, turtles, ducks, horses, tigers, and elephants, are also sculpted.

The unique terracotta art has black pottery sculptures from Azamgarh, the glazed clay sculptures of Khurja, the geometric and flower-leaf sculptures, and the stunning blue and brown ornamentation on white backdrop created by Chinhath (Lucknow) are a few examples of such works.

Indian Rural Woman

India was rated 127th out of 146 nations in the World Economic Forum's annual gender gap report for 2023, and it has closed the gender gap overall by 64.3%. But with India having one of the lowest rates of female labour force participation (LFPR) worldwide, it stood at 142 and had only attained 36.7% in terms of economic engagement and opportunity. In rural communities all throughout the world, rural women are essential because they provide care and engage in a variety of economic activities such off-farm labour, minor trading, and subsistence farming. Rural women in most regions of the world put in a lot of work yet make relatively little money.

Since women are not permitted to own the same amount of land as males, they frequently experience prejudice. A large portion of their earnings is not directly under their control due to discrimination or unequal gender roles. Contradictions affect women in rural communities. She bears primary responsibility for overseeing the execution of domestic tasks, fostering the growth of children, attending to the wants and demands of senior family members, and other related responsibilities. On the other side, she experiences a variety of mistreatment and abuse. Girls are seen as liabilities in some of the rural areas. Some people typically hold the opinion that girls shouldn't attend school and should instead be trained to handle domestic tasks. They will eventually have to get married and give up their ability to use their education. The majority of rural women face information poverty in addition to economic poor. Sometimes they are denied the right to voice their opinions or participate in the decision-making process. The majority of women lack the necessary skills to operate machinery, which are operated by males.

As we know from various studies that rural women also have the same contribution in the economy as men, hence there is a need to give good training and education to women so that they can uplift themselves and their families

Research Methodology

The nature of research is both exploratory and descriptive. This study is based on secondary source of data. Data collected from books, published reports of Government, NABARD, DWCR, census surveys, newspapers, literature reviews, studies and journals available online.

Result and Discussion

Role of Terracotta in Gorakhpur Economy:

Aurangabad, in Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh, has become a center of fine technique of terracotta craft. The region has a long history of producing fine clay toys and ornaments that are renowned for their creative skills. The terracotta artisans of Aurangabad have developed their abilities over many generations, and they now produce a wide variety of exquisite terracotta objects that are in demand not only in India but also in other regions of the world. The production process combines traditional methods with modern technology. Clay, the primary material, is molded by hand into various forms, with individual parts being prepared separately and later assembled to create the final piece. Surface decoration is often done by female artisans who decorate terracotta objects with intricate patterns, clay coils, beads, bells and foliage. The terracotta artistry of Aurangabad not only showcases the cultural heritage of the region but also contributes significantly to the livelihood of many families, keeping this time-honored craft alive and thriving.

Terracotta plays an important role in the economy of Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh, primarily as a traditional handicraft, which has gained recognition and support through various initiatives. Terracotta is the main handicraft of Gorakhpur, which contributes about Rs 1.5

crore annually to the economy of the district. This craft has recently received a Geographical Indication (GI) tag, which further enhances its value and marketability. Local artisans produce a variety of objects, including decorative sculptures and utilitarian products such as flower pots and tiles, using locally obtained clay known as "kabis" clay.

One District One Product Scheme for Gorakhpur District:

The "One District One Product" (ODOP) initiative launched by the government aims to promote traditional crafts including terracotta. The scheme provides financial assistance and market development assistance to artisans, thereby helping to sustain and develop the terracotta industry in Gorakhpur. Establishment of clusters for terracotta production is also underway, with a proposed investment of Rs 3.69 crore to promote the sector.

In Gorakhpur, especially in villages like Aurangabad and Gulariha, about 200 households are engaged in terracotta production. This craft not only serves as a source of income, but also preserves cultural heritage and provides employment opportunities within these communities.

Rural women condition in Gorakhpur:

The condition of rural women in Gorakhpur is quite bad. Most of the women are illiterate. Gorakhpur's literacy rate was almost 70.83% as of the 2011 Census, with 81.80% of men and 59.36% of women being literate. This suggests a considerable gender gap, with female literacy falling well short of male literacy. They depend on the men in their family for their expenses, so that they have to take the consent of the men before taking any decision. Most of the women work in informal sectors. They neither get salary commensurate with their work nor do they get any facilities. Due to which they do not even pay attention to their health and suffer from various types of diseases. Women often face domestic violence and social discrimination in their homes and communities, yet they are unable to raise their voice in this regard due to public shame and fear of society. Although self-help groups (SHGs) have emerged as a means for women to achieve financial independence, overall participation in these groups is low. The reach of government initiatives aimed at economically empowering women has been inconsistent, with targets for setting up new SHGs often not met due to logistical challenges and pandemic-related restrictions.

While some initiatives have been taken aimed at improving the status of rural women in Gorakhpur, significant barriers remain related to economic stability, education, health, and social equality. Tackling these challenges is important to enhance the overall well-being and empowerment of rural women in the region.

Need to have Self Dependence for Rural Woman:

The available literature explore, the literacy rate of rural women is very low and the stereotypes and superstitions of the society have kept them stuck. Therefore, considering the present environment, it is very important to bring change in the status of women because women are an integral part of the society. If the society has to progress then women will have to be connected to the mainstream and efforts will have to be made for their empowerment. To make women self-dependent, they can be given training in various arts like sewing, embroidery, weaving art, organic farming, handicrafts, sculpture, pottery etc. Local arts play an important role in uplifting the status of rural women by providing economic opportunities, enhancing their social status and promoting self-expression. Engaging in local arts helps women make and sell handmade products, which can significantly increase their income. For example, women involved in traditional crafts like Madhubani painting, Black pottery, Terracotta pottery, Chikankari, Patola weaving etc have earned substantial earnings from both national and international markets, thereby improving their financial conditions and supporting their families. The integration of local arts into the lives of rural women is a powerful means of economic and social empowerment. By providing opportunities for income generation, skill development and community building, local arts help raise the status of women in society while preserving cultural heritage. As these women flourish through their artistic endeavours, they contribute to broader social changes that promote gender equality and empowerment.

Role of Terracotta in uplifting Rural woman's Economic status in Gorakhpur:

In Gorakhpur, the use terracotta as a local art form is crucial in the economic empowerment of women. It is not only helping in making women self-reliant but also in their community development and protecting cultural heritage. The major initiatives and successes that are working in this direction:

1. Source of livelihood

Terracotta art of Gorakhpur, a traditional method of making clay objects, has become an important source of income for women. Many women are trained in this art and selling their products in local and international markets.

2. Self Help Group (SHG)

Women come together through self-help groups (SHGs) to produce terracotta products. These groups provide not only financial assistance but also training and marketing opportunities. For example, women through SHGs are being able to sell their products on online platforms, increasing both their reach and sales.

3. Government schemes

The Uttar Pradesh government has launched several schemes to empower women, such as the "One District, One Product" (ODOP) scheme. Under this scheme, terracotta has been recognized as a major product in Gorakhpur, providing an opportunity to local women to grow their businesses.

4. Training and skill development

In Gorakhpur, women are being given special training to make terracotta products. For example, in the Bhathat area, women are taking training in making art works on wheel. During this training, they are being taught all aspects from clay preparation to dyeing, thereby increasing their efficiency.

5. Source of Income

Women are now actively participating in the manufacturing of terracotta products, which has improved their income. For example, when the training started in Jungle Ekla Number Two, more than 30 women participated. These types of activities have given them the opportunity to improve the economic condition of their families

6. Market Access and Marketing

Women have taken steps towards selling terracotta products in local markets and online platforms. This gives them a chance to increase the sales of their products and increase their income. Apart from this, the assistance given by the government and various NGOs has also developed their marketing skills.

7. Social change

Improving the economic status of women is not limited to financial gains alone; It also increases their confidence and decision-making ability. Many women have now started participating in village Panchayat elections, which is a sign of their empowerment.

Improvement in the economic status of women through terracotta art in Gorakhpur is moving in a positive direction. Initiatives like training, collective efforts, and market access are not only increasing their incomes but also encouraging social change. Thus, terracotta art has become an important means of self-reliance and empowerment for women.

Challenges encountered by Rural woman for undertaking Terracotta as livelihood:

Rural women engaged in terracotta craftsmanship in Gorakhpur face many challenges that hinder their ability to establish a sustainable livelihood. Here are some of the major obstacles:

1. Limited access to resources

Raw material:

Access to quality raw materials is often a significant challenge for women artisans. Many rely on local suppliers, and fluctuations in availability can disrupt production schedules.

Constant supply shortages can lead to delays and reduced production, affecting their income.

Financial Resources

Women often struggle to obtain financial support to start or expand their terracotta businesses. The traditional banking system may not adequately meet their needs, and they may lack collateral or credit history, limiting their access to credit.

2. Market relations:

Poor Market Access

Many women artisans find it difficult to access wider markets due to inadequate marketing strategies and poor market contacts. They often depend on local sales, which may not yield sufficient profits. Without proper marketing channels, their products may not receive the visibility needed to attract buyers.

Competing With Machine-Made Products

The rise of machine-made terracotta and ceramic products poses a significant threat to traditional artisans. These products are often cheaper and more readily available, making it difficult for handmade goods to compete on price and accessibility.

3. Lack of training and skill development:

Inadequate Training Programs

While some training initiatives exist, many women still lack access to comprehensive skills development programs that can enhance their craftsmanship and vocational skills. Without adequate training in modern technologies or business management, they may struggle to innovate or improve their products.

Digital Literacy

As the market is increasingly moving towards online platforms, many rural women lack the digital skills required to effectively market their products online. This gap limits their ability to reach a wider audience and take advantage of e-commerce opportunities.

4. Socio-Cultural Barriers:

Traditional Gender Roles

Deeply rooted cultural norms often restrict women's participation in economic activities outside the home. Many women face social pressure to prioritize domestic responsibilities over professional aspirations, which may limit their participation in terracotta production.

Discrimination And Lack of Support

Women artisans may face discrimination within the artisan community or face challenges in gaining recognition for their work. This lack of support can reduce their motivation and hinder their professional development.

5. Influence of External Factors:

Economic Instability

External factors such as economic recession or crisis (such as the COVID-19 pandemic) may disproportionately affect rural women engaged in terracotta crafts. These events may reduce demand for handmade goods, further increasing financial instability.

To enhance the livelihood of rural women involved in terracotta craftsmanship in Gorakhpur, it is necessary to address these challenges through targeted interventions. This includes improving access to resources, developing stronger market linkages,

providing comprehensive training programs, and promoting enabling environments that support women's economic participation. By overcoming these barriers, it is possible to empower women artisans and promote sustainable livelihoods through their crafts.

Conclusion

The relationship between the local art of terracotta and the economic empowerment of rural women in Gorakhpur is important and multifaceted. The terracotta industry not only serves as a source of income for women artisans but also plays an important role in enhancing their social status and promoting community development.

Terracotta craftsmanship in Gorakhpur has emerged as an important means for rural women to achieve economic independence. By engaging in this traditional art, women are able to generate income, which directly contributes to the financial stability of their families. The recognition of Gorakhpur terracotta as a Geographical Indication (GI) has further enhanced its marketability, helping women artisans access wider markets and gain recognition for their skills. Additionally, the integration of digital technology and Self Help Groups (SHGs) has empowered these women by providing them with the necessary training, resources and support networks. This empowerment not only improves their economic conditions but also boosts self-confidence, leadership skills and social mobility.

Suggestions for the future Study Several measures can be implemented to further enhance the role of terracotta art in uplifting the economic status of rural women in Gorakhpur:

Advanced Training Programs: Implement comprehensive training programs that focus on both traditional techniques and modern business practices. It will equip women with the necessary skills to improve product quality and marketing strategies.

Access to financial resources: To facilitate easy access to micro finance and credit facilities for women artisans. This financial assistance can help them invest in better equipment, materials, and marketing efforts.

Market Development Initiative: Establish partnerships with local and national markets to create platforms to showcase terracotta products. Organizing exhibitions and fairs can help in increasing visibility and sales opportunities for artisans.

Digital Literacy Programme: To provide training in digital literacy to women to enable them to leverage online platforms for marketing their products. This will expand their customer base beyond local markets.

Supportive policy framework: Advocate for policies to support women's participation in the handicrafts sector, including subsidies, grants and incentives for sustainable practices in terracotta production.

Community Awareness Campaign: Run awareness campaigns to promote the value of hand-made terracotta products, emphasize their cultural significance and support local artisans.

References

1. *Almusaed, A., Yitmen, I., & Almssad, A. (2024). Contemporary Innovations and Sustainable Practices in the Application of Clay Materials within Architectural Design and Construction Methodologies.*
2. *Das, J., Sengupta, S., Bhattacharjee, S., & Saha, B. An Interactive Design Concept for Sustainability of Terracotta Production.*
3. *Gautam, R. K., & Mishra, K. (2016). Study on rural women entrepreneurship in India: Issues and challenges. International journal of applied research, 2(2), 33-36.*
4. *Gupta, S. et al. (2020). "Challenges faced by traditional artisans: a review." IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, 1011(1), 012092.*
5. *Khan, M.K.I. et al. (2018). "Terracotta handicraft business in Bangladesh: development potentiality and prospects." Asian Journal of Public Affairs, 11(1), 33-50*
6. *Kumar, V. (2019). INDIAN JOURNAL OF ARCHAEOLOGY.*
7. *Menon, J., & Varma, S. (2010). Reading archaeological evidence: ceramic and terracotta production at Indor Khera, Uttar Pradesh (200 BCE–500 CE). Indian Historical Review, 37(2), 187-216.*
8. *Mitra, A. (2018). Male migrants and women farmers in Gorakhpur. Economic and Political Weekly, 53(17), 55-62.*
9. *Rai, M. (2017). Market Opportunities In Indian Handicraft Industry. International Journal of Research in Social Sciences, 7(4), 616-623.*
10. *Singh, A., Shukla, A., & Kashyap, P. " FROM TRADITION TO TECHNOLOGY: STRATEGIES FOR SAFEGUARDING GORAKHPUR'S CULTURE AND HERITAGE.*
11. *Stratton, M. (1986). The terracotta industry: its distribution, manufacturing processes and products. Industrial archaeology review, 8(2), 194-214.*
12. *TRIPATHI, K., & SINGH, D. R. Financial Practices and Barriers among Rural Women of Gorakhpur District.*
13. *Yadav, U.S, Tripathi, R., Tripathi, M.A., & Kushwaha, J. (2022). Performance of women artisans as entrepreneurs in odop in uttar pradesh to boost economy: strategies and away towards global handicraft index for small business. Academy of Marketing Studies Journal, 26(1), 1-19.*
14. *Yadav, U. S., Tripathi, R., & Tripathi, M. A. (2022). Indian small industries (terracotta of gorakhpur and bankura) and women artisan in digital and covid-19*

- era: a case study on the traditional handicraft in uttar pradesh. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 22, 358-370.
15. Wendt, J. A., & Tügen, E. (2022). A. The art of terracotta from the perspective of cultural geography: Tavas case (Denizli/Turkey). *GeoJ. Tour. Geosites*, 43, 1005-1012.
 16. <https://sukarya.org/ofa-empowering-women-and-making-them-self-reliant/>
 17. <https://www.jagran.com/uttar-pradesh/gorakhpur-city-terracotta-artifacts-will-flourish-with-the-skills-of-women-skill-is-being-made-by-training-22181695.html>
 18. <https://www.uniindia.com/news/north/women-empowerment-up-yogi/3123582.html>
 19. <https://theprint.in/india/in-ups-gorakhpur-women-have-taken-the-lead-to-run-the-family-with-a-little-self-help/718121/>
 20. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/lucknow/govt-schemes-helped-us-in-pursuit-of-self-reliance/articleshow/81420265.cms>
 21. <https://www.ideasforindia.in/topics/social-identity/womens-economic-empowerment-and-domestic-violence-hindi.html>
 22. <https://www.hindustantimes.com/cities/others/govt-committed-to-self-reliance-of-women-says-adityanath-101705162519017.html>
 23. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/news-stories/feature-story/2022/10/three-challenges-for-rural-women-amid-a-cost-of-living-crisis>